

Medicated Chewing gums a novel oral drug delivery method: A review

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Abstract

Antacid chewing gum is a novel way to managing gastroesophageal reflux disease (GERD) and acid-related disease. Unlike typical tablets or liquid formulations, chewing gum stimulates saliva production, which improves acid neutralization and esophageal evacuation. Antacid substances like calcium carbonate, magnesium hydroxide, or sodium bicarbonate can be added to a gum base to provide quick and easy relief from heartburn and indigestion. Furthermore, extended chewing may help to provide long-term symptom alleviation by generating bicarbonate-rich saliva. This review looks at the formulation, mechanism of action, clinical efficacy, benefits, and potential downsides of antacid chewing gum against traditional antacid delivery systems. Furthermore, current developments in functional chewing gums, such as the use of probiotics and herbal extracts, are highlighted.

Keywords: Antacid chewing gum, salivary stimulation, Medicated Chewing gum, calcium carbonate

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, chewing gum, as a sweet and delightful confectionary, has demonstrated its promise as an excellent delivery vehicle for pharmaceutical and neutra-ceuticals . In terms of patient convenience, chewing gum is inconspicuous, and its administration without water encourages greater compliance. A chewing gum formulation is an ideal alternative for acute medicine because it is portable. Studies have demonstrated that even non-medicated chewing gum enhances saliva flow and raises plaque pH, hence preventing tooth decay[1] Medicated chewing gum is now a well-established dosage form, as stated in the European Pharmacopoeia. It has several advantages, including a quick onset of action, avoidance of hepatic first pass metabolism for drugs taken buccally, and probably lower dosage requirements, resulting in fewer adverse effects.[2.]

Heartburn, acid reflux, and indigestion are common issues, with many people seeking medical help for gastrointestinal disorders. Doctors often recommend over-the-counter antacid tablets and liquids for these conditions. However, these traditional forms have drawbacks related to taste, portability, and practicality, especially when patients are on the move. Chewing gum, a convenient and accepted form, has become a preferred delivery system for many developers. Using known

antacid agents in chewing gum offers an effective, convenient, and well-tolerated method of neutralizing stomach acid.[3,4]In order to provide a chewable substitute for traditional antacid treatments, this project aims to create an antacid chewing gum and investigate its physicochemical properties and acid-neutralizing ability. These would combine the simplicity and convenience of chewing gum with the therapeutic benefits of antacids.[5] consumers who suffer from heartburn and acid reflux spend billions of dollars on over-the-counter (OTC) treatments to get relief. Antacids are a significant class of OTC medications that are offered all over the world. [6] Antacids relieve the symptoms of GERD (Gastroesophageal reflux disease) heartburn, hyperacidity, acid reflux, and upset stomach that are related to these disorders. [7] Antacids neutralize excess hydrochloric acid (HCl) in gastric juice and inhibit the proteolytic enzyme pepsin. [8] An antacid that raises gastric pH from 1.5 to 3.5 can reduce gastric acid concentration by 100-fold. [9] According to a few studies, some antacids can be used safely during pregnancy since they have local rather than systemic effects. [10,11,12]

Antacids are divided into two categories: systemic or absorbable and non-systemic or non-absorbable antacids. Absorbable antacids are easily absorbed into the systemic circulation and can cause both electrolytic and alkaline changes. Non-absorbable antacids include aluminum hydroxide, aluminum phosphate, calcium carbonate, and magnesium hydroxide, which are not well absorbed; for example, only 15% to 30% of calcium and 5% to 10% of magnesium are absorbed from their respective antacid formulations. [13-15]

Each antacid ingredient has a unique mechanism with the ultimate goal of acid neutralization (figer1) [16-20]

Figure 1.

Calcium carbonate: Calcium carbonate interacts with stomach HCl to form calcium chloride, CO₂, and water. Calcium ions relieve heartburn by increasing peristalsis in the esophagus and pushing acid into the stomach. Carbonate anions bind to free protons (H⁺) from HCl, lowering H⁺ concentrations in the stomach and rising pH. In the alkaline conditions of the small intestine, soluble calcium chloride is converted back to calcium carbonate and excreted in stool, reducing its absorption. [14]

Sodium bicarbonate: Sodium bicarbonate, a fast-acting antacid, combines with gastric HCl in the stomach to form sodium chloride, carbon dioxide, and water. Excess bicarbonate quickly passes into the small intestine, where it is absorbed. Sodium bicarbonate is commonly mixed with citric acid. This combination interacts instantly with water to form a sodium citrate solution, releasing

carbon dioxide. Sodium citrate is a fast-acting acid neutralizer that, in appropriate amounts, can elevate stomach pH.

Magnesium salts: Magnesium hydroxide rapidly interacts with stomach HCl, producing magnesium chloride and water. Magnesium carbonate interacts with stomach HCl to form magnesium chloride, CO₂, and water. Magnesium trisilicate dissolves slowly and combines with gastric HCl to form magnesium chloride, silicon dioxide, and water.

Aluminum salts: Aluminum hydroxide interacts with gastric HCl to form aluminium chloride and water. Aluminum carbonate interacts with stomach HCl to form aluminum chloride, CO₂, and water. Aluminum phosphate interacts with gastric HCl to form aluminum chloride and phosphoric acid.

Advantages of Medicated chewing gums

1. Higher effectiveness compared to other oral administration techniques. [21,22]
2. Removal of gum can stop drug delivery. [21,22]
3. Reduces the risk of overdose when consumed in whole. [21,22]
4. Requires no water for drinking. [21,22]
5. Protect vulnerable medications against chemical or enzymatic attacks in the gastrointestinal tract.[22]
6. Systemic and local medication delivery. [21,22]
7. Chewing gum is well-accepted by adolescents and teenagers, and its low first-pass impact allows for a lower dose compared to other oral administration systems. [21,22]
8. Rapid delivery with less side effects.[21-23]
9. Lowers the chance of stomach mucosal intolerance.[22]
10. Excellent resistance to light, air, and moisture.[21]
11. Tonsillectomy resulted in reduced pain and difficulty swallowing.[24]
12. Enhancing workplace performance and cognitive function. [26]
13. Antidiabetic medication reduced hypoglycemic shocks.[25]
14. Increased blood flow to the brain improves alertness.[27]

Disadvantages of Medicated chewing gums

1. Drug disappears in the oral cavity after saliva dilution. [30,28]
2. Short administration time owing to eating, chatting, and drinking. [30,28]
3. Allergic response to artificial sweeteners.[29]
4. Continuous tension on the jaw might lead to temporomandibular joint condition. [25,29]
5. Sugar causes tooth decay. [25,29]
6. Underage children can choke after ingesting gum.[25]

COMPOSITION OF ANTACID CHEWING GUM:-

Antacid chewing gum is a particular composition intended to alleviate heartburn and acid reflux. The gum works by delivering antacid components in a convenient, chewable form, providing both mechanical and chemical means of neutralizing stomach acid. [31-33]

Ingredients:-

1. GumBase (30-40%)

Provides a chewable matrix. The gum base is commonly composed of natural or synthetic resins such as polyisobutylene or polyvinyl acetate.

2. Antacid Agents (15-20%)

Calcium Carbonate (CaCO_3) is a fast-acting antacid that neutralizes gastric acid. Magnesium Hydroxide (Mg(OH)_2) is a mild laxative that balances the constipating effect of calcium carbonate. The best antacid to use depends on the desired neutralizing capacity and side effects.

3. Sweeteners (5-10%)

Sorbitol, Xylitol, Mannitol, or Sucralose: Used to conceal the gritty taste of antacids and create a pleasant chewing experience. Sugar-free sweeteners are recommended for dental health.

4. Flavoring Agents (2-5%)

Peppermint, spearmint, or fruit flavors enhance taste and texture, making the product more appealing to consumers.

5. Softening Agents (2-5%)

Glycerin or lecithin: Prevent the gum from hardening and keep it flexible throughout storage and use.

6. Binder/Plasticizer (3-8%)

Corn Syrup, Hydrogenated Starch Hydrolysates: Enhance texture and cohesiveness.

7. Optional Ingredients:

Colorants: Titanium Dioxide for whiteness or FD&C-approved dyes for aesthetic appeal.

Lubricants: Stearic Acid helps in preventing sticking during manufacturing.

METHOD OF PREPARATION OF ANTACID CHEWING GUM

- Fusion method
- Cooling, grinding, and tableting method
- Direct compression process

Fusion method

This method involves melting the gum components and combining them with active chemicals and additives in a kettle mixer. The gum is then pushed through rollers. Sugar alternatives are added to prevent gum from becoming sticky and boost flavoring. The gum is then chilled for 2 days. The gum is sliced to the desired size and shape, then chilled at specific temperatures and humidity levels. [34,35]

Limitation

- Temperature elevated during the melting process make restriction to the use of heat-sensitive drug
- Un precise shape, weight of the resulted dosage form
- Difficult control of uniformity and accuracy of drug dosing due to highly viscous gum use.
- Due to high moisture content, 2–8% of chewing gum is difficult to formulate to the tablet because its composition would sticky to the grinding machine with difficulty to compress.[36]

Cooling, Grinding, and Tableting Method

The composition of Chewing gum is cooled to -15°C , where it remains brittle for the next grinding phase. The refrigerated substance is then crushed into fine particles. To achieve more efficient cooling, a mixture of chewing gum, silica, and solid carbon dioxide is first ground in a mill grinder, followed by further silica and solid carbon dioxide grinding in the second grinding process. These

two grinding phases retain the chewing gum's composition at a low temperature, while the presence of solid carbon dioxide improves grinding efficiency. To minimize product agglomeration, anticaking agents such as precipitated silica dioxide can be blended with solid carbon dioxide and chewing gum composition before the grinding step[37]. A fluidized bed reactor (FBR) is used to make gum tablets by removing the coolant from the powder mixture, which is then blended with lubricant, binder, and sweeteners in a high shear mixer. FBR rebuilds the powder in the granules and coats the granule with a coating agent, reducing particle agglomeration.[38]

Direct Compression Process

- Direct compression Chewing gum can be compressed directly on a standard tableting machine, allowing for the speedy and cost-effective creation of a gum delivery system.
- Polyols and/or sugars are mixed with gum base to produce directly compressible, free-flowing powdered gum.
- These can be compressed into tablets using a standard tablet press.
- The items are harder than their counterparts, and texture examination indicates that they collapse under pressure.
- These chewing gums can contain more active substances than standard extruded gums, and the low temperature protects sensitive bioactivity and phytochemical components. Additionally, the decreased moisture content increases the shelf life of the active molecules. Release is faster than with traditional gums.[39]

EVALUATION OF ANTACID CHEWING GUM

Drug content: - About 20 mL of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer were added to one gram of the formulation in a mortar, and the mixture was then triturated. A conical flask was used to hold this. Using an orbital shaking incubator set to 100 rpm, 30 mL of pH 6.8 phosphate buffer was added and thoroughly shaken for approximately three hours. After that, it was filtered, and the same buffer was used to make the filtrate markable. Adequate dilutions were prepared, and the absorbance at 254 nm was used to calculate the drug concentration.

Visual Appearance:- The prepared chewing gum was visually evaluated for taste, homogeneity, color, smoothness, and transparency.[40]

Thickness Measurement:- The mean thickness of each produced gummy was assessed using a digital venire caliper (milliliter screw gauge).[41]

Weight Variation:-To determine the weight of each manufactured gummy, a digital electrical balance was used. The mean and standard deviation were then calculated.[42]

Percentage Moisture Loss and Moisture Content:- Each gummy was weighted and placed in a desiccator with 1-g of anhydrous CaCl_2 . After three days, they were removed and re-weighed. The percentage moisture loss and moisture content were calculated using the following equation.[43]

Percentage moisture loss = $\frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{initial weight}}$

Percentage moisture content = $\frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{initial weight}}$

Hardness Test:- The hardness of the candy was determined by estimating the forces required to smash the gummy using the Monsanto hardness tester.[44]

Surface pH:- To conduct this test, cut the gum into four pieces and place them in 50ml of DW. After 10 minutes, use a digital pH meter to record the pH.[45]

In vitro Drug Release Study:- To perform this test, use a suitable volume of 0.1 N HCL at 37°C and 50 rpm in a dissolution apparatus type II. At regular intervals, the sample was removed from the jar, refilled with the same volume of dissolving media, filtered, and examined using a UV-visible Spectrophotometer to determine its maximum concentration.[46]

Acid-Neutralizing Capacity:- The acid-neutralizing capacity (ANC) of an antacid refers to how much acid it can neutralize. The United States Pharmacopoeia (USP) defines the ANC test as a back-titration method that uses sodium hydroxide (0.5N solution) to a pH 3.5 endpoint to determine the number of milliequivalents of acid (hydrochloric acid 1N solution) neutralized by the minimum labeled dosage (MLD) of an antacid [47].

CONCLUSION

Chewing gum is an effective medicine delivery strategy due to its self-administration and ability to be consumed without water. It provides various benefits compared to Chewable tablets and lozenges release pharmacological substances from the gum, which can be utilized to treat local oral diseases or systemically following absorption through the buccal mucosa, Heartburn, acid reflux, and indigestion are common issues, with many people seeking medical help for gastrointestinal disorders. Doctors often recommend over-the-counter antacid tablets and liquids for these conditions. However, these traditional forms have drawbacks related to taste, portability, and practicality, especially when patients are on the move. Chewing gum, a convenient and accepted form, has become a preferred delivery system for many developers. Using known antacid agents in chewing gum offers an effective, convenient, and well-tolerated method of neutralizing stomach acid

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